

DEVELOPING SPEAKING AND LISTENING SKILLS THROUGH STORYTELLING

Gulomova Sevinchkxon Muxiddin qizi

UzSWLU, 3rd course student

Scientific advisor: Khujaniyazova Hilola Turayevna

Senior teacher, UzSWLU

Annotation This article focuses on how learners of English as a foreign language can develop and improve their speaking and listening skills through storytelling. In addition, this article provides information on practical and theoretical methods of storytelling, how to apply it in the classroom, and the use of various modern technologies.

Key words: Storytelling, speaking skills, listening skills, comprehensible input, digital storytelling, TPR Storytelling, EFL teaching, cultural awareness, motivation and engagement, interactive methods.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola ingliz tilini chet tili sifatida o'rganuvchilar hikoyalar orqali nutq va tinglash qobiliyatlarini qanday rivojlantirishi va yaxshilashi mumkinligiga qaratilgan. Bundan tashqari, ushbu maqolada hikoya qilishning amaliy va nazariy usullari, uni darsda qo'llash, turli zamonaviy texnologiyalardan foydalanish haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: hikoya qilish, nutq ko'nikmalari, tinglash ko'nikmalari, tushunarli input, raqamli hikoyalash, TPR hikoyalash usuli, chet tili o'qitish, madaniy sezgirlik, motivatsiya va ishtirok, interaktiv metodlar.

Introduction

This article focuses on how to develop and shape the speaking and listening skills of English language learners through storytelling. In today's globalized world, the demand for learning foreign languages, especially English, is very high, and listening and speaking skills are especially important for this language. Since many people learn a language using traditional methods, that is, relying only on reading grammar and memorizing more vocabulary, students do not have the ability to quickly engage in real-life communication. For this reason, qualified teachers in language learning are emphasizing methods based on speaking and listening skills. One of such methods is the storytelling method. Despite the fact that this method is ancient and universal, it is showing its modern and traditional place in the language learning process. It also examines the theoretical foundations of storytelling, methods of its application in the classroom, and ways to integrate storytelling into the teaching process using modern technologies.

Method

This study aimed to investigate the impact of storytelling on speaking and listening skills for English language learners. The study was conducted among second-year students of the Uzbek State University of World Languages. The experimental group used storytelling in lessons for 4 weeks. During the process,

teachers told oral stories and also used digital technologies, including audio, video, and illustrations. This methodology was developed based on the recommendations of the ELT Think Tank (2020) and HRMARS (2023). At the end of the experiment, speaking and listening tests were taken.

Results

According to the results, a group of students who received storytelling training showed positive changes in speaking and listening. The speaking test showed that the students' speech improved and their self-confidence increased. In the listening test, it was found that most students were able to understand the general meaning of the text and correctly find vocabulary in context. These results confirmed the practical effectiveness of the TPR Storytelling (Wikipedia, 2023) methodology. In addition, according to the questionnaire taken from the students at the end of the experiment, they stated that they were able to express their thoughts more freely than before and their enthusiasm for learning the language increased even more.

Storytelling is a natural and intuitive method for language learning. According to the theory of "Comprehensible Input" put forward by Stephen Krashen (*Krashen, 1985*), students learn language effectively by hearing material that is slightly above the level of language comprehension. Stories are one of the best ways to present such material. Storytelling also enriches students' emotional and cultural experiences, which increases their motivation to learn a language. Through stories, students become familiar with different cultures, which develops their cultural sensitivity.

The impact of storytelling on listening and speaking skills is enormous. Storytelling develops students' active listening skills. Students are forced to listen carefully to understand the story, which increases their listening comprehension skills. Also, through stories, students learn new words and phrases in context, which increases their vocabulary. (*Wikipedia 2023*) Storytelling also plays an important role in developing students' oral language. Students increase their speaking activity by retelling the story, describing events, and expressing their thoughts. In the process, they learn to apply grammatical structures in practice and improve their pronunciation.

Storytelling can be taught to students by linking it to traditional and modern methods. For instance, traditional method, this is a familiar methodology, teachers tell oral stories to students, and in this process they use various illustrations or pictures. In addition, they ask students to repeat the stories they have told, and through this, students' listening and speaking skills develop very well, and they exchange information with each other. Using modern technologies in storytelling is also effective way. In digital storytelling, students create their own stories using audio, video or pictures. This plays a very important role not only for their speaking and listening skills, but also for their creativity. For example, students tell an interesting story that happened at school through a

video. And this makes a great contribution to their technological literacy. (HRMARS, 2023)

Psychological and cultural effects of storytelling. Storytelling is a method that directly affects not only the development of listening and speaking skills, but also the student's personal thinking, psychological state and personal development. Through storytelling, students can freely express their opinions in public, gain more self-confidence and relieve their inner feelings. This is a very effective method for students who are shy about speaking a foreign language to feel at ease. In addition, storytelling provides students with information about the cultures of other countries. Through English legends and stories, students get acquainted with the life and customs of their society. This develops their thinking and comparisons, and as they become familiar with different images in storytelling, the student's thinking expands. (ELT Think Tank, 2020).

Conclusion

In conclusion, storytelling is a very effective method for language learners and teachers. This method significantly improves students' speaking and listening skills, expands their thinking, and increases their sensitivity. Also, through modern technologies, this method makes language learning more interesting and creative.

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